

MEASURES TO PROVIDE PSYCHOLOGICAL SUPPORT TO WOMEN EXPERIENCED
BY VIOLENCE

Rakhmatov Sirojbek Israil uglu

Psychologist of the National Agency for Social Protection
under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan,
Kosan District "Inson" Social Services Center

Abstract. Psychological violence in the family affects the psyche of family members, which leads to psychological trauma. This article highlights the fact that cases of violence against women are causing psychological and physical oppression of women, as well as the violation of their human rights. The article also emphasizes the relevance of providing legal and psychological assistance.

Keywords: violence, domestic violence against women, family, gender equality, psychological assistance, women's rights, social protection.

Introduction. Domestic violence is the most common form of violence against women. It negatively affects women throughout their lives, from sex-selective abortion of the fetus to suicide and violence. According to the World Health Organization, as of March 1, 2024, the percentage of women who have experienced physical or sexual violence, or both, by an intimate partner is found to be between 15% and 71%, with the majority between 29% and 62%. [7]

Discussion. Violence is any act (inaction) that occurs, or is likely to occur, of physical, psychological, sexual or economic violence against women, resulting in, or threatening to cause, harm to their life, health, sexual integrity, honour, dignity or other rights and freedoms protected by law.

Violence causes serious harm to the health and psyche of women, especially pregnant women. It would not be wrong to say that such atrocities do not only occur by chance or as a result of wars, but are also deliberate actions taken to deny the dignity, rights and freedoms of women, and to subjugate and subjugate them. [1] Common types of violence include:

1. Physical violence
2. Sexual violence
3. Psychological violence
4. Economic violence

Physical violence is the infliction of bodily injuries of varying severity, endangerment, failure to provide assistance to a person whose life is in danger, committing other violent offenses, physical impact or threatening to use other measures of such impact. Examples include: [2]

- Slapping, kicking, pushing, punching;
- Pushing with a blow;
- Throwing various sharp objects and things;
- Threatening or injuring with a weapon;
- Physically preventing someone from leaving the house;
- Not letting them sleep at night, etc.

Psychological violence is defined as any act or omission that insults, slanders, threatens, degrades, controls, or threatens a woman's honor and dignity, or that causes fear for her safety, inability to defend herself, or harms her mental health. Examples of psychological violence include [3].

- Failure to acknowledge feelings and emotions;

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-5

- Making fun of her thoughts;
- Ignoring the victim's feelings as a punishment, and other
- situations.

Literature review. Russian scholar I.Shakhov views domestic violence not as a simple quarrel or internal family issue, but as a serious social problem that threatens the life of society. In his opinion, "Domestic violence is a set of behaviors that have a tendency to escalate and are likely to recur"[3]. One of the most important aspects of this approach is the gradual escalation and periodic recurrence of violence. That is, what initially began with simple verbal insults turns into physical or sexual abuse over time. This process is increasingly accepted as normal and has a negative impact on the mental and physical well-being of all family members, especially children.

There are several factors contributing to the increase in violence against women in modern families, including economic, technological, social and cultural changes, as well as gender inequalities. These factors together can exacerbate, complicate and expand domestic violence.

The main causes of violence against women are associated with many social, psychological, cultural and legal factors.

L. Berkowitz considered "violence to be actions that cause or have the potential to cause harm to another person, in any of their forms and manifestations, including physical, mental and economic harm"[4].

E.N. Volkov, considering the essence of "psychological violence", compared it with the concepts of "psychological aggression" and "psychological harm". Psychological aggression is a socio-psychological impact aimed at insulting, intimidating, creating dependence, exploiting or harming another person. Considering psychological violence through the prism of the concepts of "violence" and "aggression", it emphasizes the socio-psychological effects that push a person to unusual behavior, violate the individual boundaries of the individual, and lead to a psychological state[2].

According to E.P. Agapova, domestic violence or violence in the family is understood as intentional infliction of physical and/or psychological harm to family members, including threats, coercion, and deprivation of personal freedom to commit such acts[3].

D.P. Gil "Violence is the use of physical force by people to resolve conflicts between themselves, in the process of which one party intentionally inflicts or threatens to inflict harm on another." D.P. Gil's definition defines violence as purposeful, that is, intentional actions intended to harm another person[5].

Conclusion and analysis. The consequences of domestic violence today are very wide and diverse, with deep-seated symptoms. These consequences have long-term psychological effects not only for the women who are victims of violence, but also for their children and society itself.

We divide the main consequences of domestic violence into the following groups:

Group 1, women who are victims of domestic violence face many physical and mental problems. They face depression, anxiety, low self-esteem, psychological trauma and sometimes physical injuries. Such women often experience life dissatisfaction, social isolation and, in some cases, even suicide.

Group 2, children who witness violence or are exposed to violence in the family experience serious changes in their psychological and emotional state. They may sometimes display fear, anxiety, low self-esteem, aggression or fearful behaviour. Witnessing violence has a negative impact on children's development and increases the likelihood of repeating the cycle of violence in their own families.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-5

Group 3, domestic violence undermines social stability in society. Women and children who are subjected to violence often participate less in society and live in social isolation. This reduces their ability to work in society and creates an additional burden on health, education and social services.

According to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Protection of Women from Harassment and Violence", adopted on August 17, 2019, the main directions of state policy in the field of protection of women from harassment and violence are as follows:[6]

- Development and implementation of gender policy, state programs and strategies in the field of protection of women from harassment and violence.
- Creation of an environment of intolerance towards harassment and violence against women in society.
- Ensuring the protection of women's rights, freedoms and legitimate interests from harassment and violence.
- Raising legal awareness and legal culture in society, strengthening the rule of law.
- Creation of effective organizational and legal mechanisms to prevent, identify and put an end to harassment and violence against women.
- take measures to eliminate the causes and conditions that lead to oppression and violence against women.

ensure cooperation between state bodies, citizens' self-government bodies, non-governmental non-profit organizations and other institutions of civil society in order to prevent oppression and violence. It is very important to provide psychological support to women who have suffered oppression and violence.

In such cases, psychological assistance is provided in the following stages: 1. Creating an environment of trust and security, the victim should feel safe. The psychologist provides her with an environment of understanding and support. Confidentiality is guaranteed.

2. Restoring initial psychological stability. The woman's feelings and experiences are listened to. Exercises are conducted to reduce anxiety, fear and depression. Breathing techniques and methods for reducing stress are taught.

3. Helping to recover from trauma and work on psychological injuries caused by violence. Psychoeducation is provided so that the woman does not feel guilty. Help is provided to restore self-confidence and independence.

4. Legal and social support. If necessary, legal advice is provided. Directions are given to contact social services and rehabilitation centers.

5. Making a plan for the future. Plans are made to take the woman's life to a new level. Advice is provided on gaining independence, finding a job, or learning a profession.

In conclusion, providing psychological support to women who have been victims of violence and oppression is essential to stabilize their mental state, restore their self-confidence, and help them start a new life. Psychological counseling, stress reduction techniques, legal and social support provide victims with the opportunity to overcome their trauma.

Xulosa kilib aytganda tazyiq va zo'raonlikdan jabrlangan ayollarga psixologik yordam ko'rsatish ularning ruhiy holatini barqarorlashtirish, o'ziga bo'lgan ishonchini tiklash va yangi hayot boshlashiga yordam berish uchun muhim ahamiyatga ega. Psixologik maslahatlar, stressni kamaytirish texnikalari, huquqiy va ijtimoiy qo'llab-quvvatlash orqali jabrlanuvchilarga travmadan chiqish imkoniyati yaratiladi.

1. Bannayev, M. S. (2022). O'zbekistonda psixologik diagnostika va psixologik korreksion faoliyatni amalga oshirishdagi muammolar va yechimlar. Science and Education, 3(6), 701–703
2. В.И.Шахов Насилие в семье: уголовно-правовое и криминологическое значение. // Автореф. дис. ...канд. юрид. наук.–Казань, 2003.
3. Лысова, А. В. Насилие в семье: учеб. пособие / А. В. Лысова. –Владивосток : Изд-во Дальневост. Ун-та, 2001. – 205 с
4. L. Berkowitz, «Aggression: Its Causes, Consequences, and Control», 1993. P-276
5. D.P. Gil, «Violence and Crime in Cross-National Perspective», 2003. P-196.
6. <https://lex.uz/acts/-4494709>
7. www.statistic.com

